

Digesting Centralized Curricula in Türkiye: How Literate are English Language Teachers?

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Abstract: One of the most essential competencies for teachers of English as a foreign language in Türkiye is the ability to implement curricula with complete comprehension in their classes, as Türkiye has mandated centralized curricula in schools. In other words, it is the teacher's responsibility to comprehend the curricula properly; otherwise, what is intended in the curricula may not be fulfilled, affecting students' learning trajectories. Nevertheless, how they conceptualize a curriculum has received little attention up until now. To fill this niche in the literature, the current study aimed to probe the level of curriculum literacy among English language teachers in state schools. In this quantitative study, data was collected through the Curriculum Literacy Inventory for Language Teachers, specifically developed in line with English language curricula in Türkiye and the Common European Framework of References for Languages by the researchers. After the pilot study, 804 English language teachers participated in the actual study. Based on the findings, the teachers exhibited a moderate level of curriculum literacy, and some significant differences were noted in certain variables. The findings can be exploited to develop interventions to raise teachers' curriculum literacy by policymakers, teacher educators and researchers.

Anahtar Sözcükler:

Öğretim programı
Öğretim program okuryazarlığı
İngilizce öğretmenleri
Öğretmen eğitimi
İngilizce öğretimi

Türkiye'de Merkezi Öğretim Programlarını Sindirmek: İngilizce Öğretmenleri Ne Kadar Okuryazar?

Özet: Türkiye'de yabancı dil olarak İngilizce öğretmenlerinin sahip olması gereken en temel yeterliklerden biri, okullarda merkezi öğretim programları uygulandığı için bunları tam olarak anlayarak sınıflarında uygulayabilmeleridir. Başka bir deyişle, öğretim programlarını doğru bir şekilde anlamak öğretmenlerin sorumluluğundadır; aksi takdirde, öğretim programlarında amaçlananlar yerine getirilemeyebilir ve bu da öğrencilerin öğrenme yolculuklarını etkileyebilir. Nitekim, bir öğretim programını nasıl anladıkları şimdiye kadar çok az ilgi görmüştür. Literatürdeki bu boşluğu doldurmak için, bu çalışma devlet okullarındaki İngilizce öğretmenlerinin öğretim programı okuryazarlığı düzeyini araştırmayı amaçlamıştır. Bu nicel çalışmada veriler, araştırmacılar tarafından Türkiye'deki İngilizce dersi öğretim programları ve Avrupa Dilleri Ortak Çerçeve Metni'ne uygun olarak geliştirilen Dil Öğretmenleri için Öğretim Programı Okuryazarlığı Envanteri aracılığıyla toplanmıştır. Pilot çalışmanın ardından, asıl çalışmaya 804 İngilizce öğretmeni katılmıştır. Bulgulara göre, öğretmenler orta düzeyde öğretim program okuryazarlığı sergilemiş ve bazı değişkenlerde önemli farklılıklar kaydedilmiştir. Bulgular, politika yapıcılar, öğretmen eğitimcileri ve araştırmacılar tarafından öğretmenlerin öğretim programı okuryazarlığını artırmaya yönelik müdahaleler geliştirmek için kullanılabilir.

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1. Introduction

Concerning the studies about English language curriculum, numerous factors that pertain to how English language teachers bring curricula into their classrooms include their beliefs, professional development, classroom size, the amount of time that is allocated for English lessons, as well as students' education levels (Bennett, 2007; Byrne, 2015; Fives & Buehl, 2016; Kaya, 2018; Ross, 2023). Still, empirical research on English language teachers' curriculum literacy is rare in the related literature. Despite the assertion that teachers need to be highly literate to effectively execute the curriculum content (Ornstein & Hunkins, 2017), English language teachers may experience difficulties due to a lack of curricular understanding in the classroom, which is deduced from the local studies in Türkiye (Er, 2006; Günel & Engin-Demir, 2012; Kuloglu & Tutus, 2022). The studies reveal that English language teachers may have some trouble in creating materials to be used in activities regarding the curriculum (Er, 2006), preparing alternative assessment tools (Günel & Engin-Demir, 2012), and adapting the contents of the curriculum to their students' level (Kuloglu & Tutus, 2022). Furthermore, a substantial quantity of research has been conducted on the viewpoints of teachers regarding the curriculum and its implementation, as well as the challenges they have encountered in Türkiye (Ayaz et al., 2019; Kırkgöz, 2008; Öztürk & Aydın, 2019; Yıldırım & Tanrıseven, 2015; Valizadeh, 2021). Teachers assert that they need to focus on grammar because they think that is what the curriculum requires (Ayaz et al., 2019; Valizadeh, 2021), and the curriculum is above the level of their students, so they cannot catch up with it (Öztürk & Aydın, 2019). In addressing the curriculum, teachers have the freedom to express their opinions when researchers ask them, but assessing the reliability of such views is crucial. Teachers' lack of curricular literacy may hinder their ability to fully articulate their thoughts, thereby biasing the research findings with their opposing views. As Rudduck (1987) suggests, teachers should have the curriculum literacy necessary for competent critique. Although obtaining their viewpoints on curriculum is worthwhile, they may not provide a whole picture of whether curriculum is effective, as how competently teachers perceive curriculum may affect their judgments about it and curriculum implementation (Ross, 2023). Therefore, investigating teachers' curriculum literacy may elucidate how English language teachers execute the curriculum.

1.1. Literature Review

1.1.1. *Curriculum Literacy*

Curriculum literacy is a sophisticated term that refers to a teacher's capacity to understand, analyze, and execute educational curriculum proficiently. Curriculum literacy fundamentally involves comprehension of the diverse elements and frameworks of a curriculum, including its objectives, content, pedagogical methods, and assessment methodologies. This understanding constitutes a fundamental ability for teachers, allowing them to effectively modify their teaching approaches to accommodate varied student demands (Aslan, 2019; Nazaree-Nia, 2023; Robertson et al., 2020). In other words, teachers have a wide range of responsibilities when it comes to curriculum and instruction. They make important decisions about which subjects to prioritize, how much time to allocate to each subject and unit, and what activities are most suitable for their students. They also create detailed lesson plans, select appropriate assessment tools, and set clear instructional goals and objectives (Oliva, 2008). Likewise, Richards (2010) emphasizes that incorporating pedagogical content knowledge in language instruction may influence teachers' ability to interpret and adjust curricular standards for effective classroom outcomes. Thereupon, teachers must be curriculum-literate to comprehend and implement the curriculum fully; otherwise, without a

thorough understanding of the curriculum and philosophy behind it, there is often a gap between what is desired and what is practiced (Schuchardt et al., 2017; Taba, 1962; Ur 2019). Therefore, curriculum interpretation can arise when rigorous curriculum analysis is combined with an understanding of theoretical choice aspects (Ben-Peretz, 1990). To put it another way, curriculum-literate teachers are those who are knowledgeable about the various elements of the curriculum, including its aims and objectives, contents, learning experiences, and evaluation processes.

Wiles and Bondi (2007) also underscored the necessity of a theoretical understanding of a curriculum. They posited that the material given in coursebooks could not correspond with the goals of a curriculum or the standardized achievement assessments administered by schools. Consequently, they proposed a six-step procedure for instructional execution that advised teachers to be aware of the conceptual underpinnings of the curriculum to carry it out in the classroom. In the initial phase, which is determining tasks and student outcomes, teachers need to be cognizant of instructional tasks and learning objectives. By the end of the school year, they must ensure that all students have accomplished the outcomes. They should modify the curriculum in the second step by probing students' motivation, interests, aptitudes, and backgrounds. At the classroom level, teachers coordinate the entire educational process in the third stage by drawing on their expertise and experiences. During the fourth phase of the cycle, it is crucial for teachers to carefully consider the various options available when it comes to administering curricula in the classroom. Factors such as students, time allocation, resources, equipment, and setting should all be considered. It is essential to be prepared for the possibility that the objectives may fail to be achieved despite having a contingency plan in place. In addition, they must analyze students' learning and the methods they employ to teach them in the fifth phase. They should possess expertise in many testing tools and demonstrate advanced proficiency in their utilization. The last step involves modifying the approach to implementing the curriculum for forthcoming instructional cycles, considering the information gathered in the previous stage. Concerning the steps proposed by Wiles and Bondi (2007), it can be deduced that teachers need to be equipped with curriculum knowledge; otherwise, their lack of this knowledge can adversely affect overall learning experiences. Hence, the level of a teacher's curriculum literacy may be of assistance when determining how effectively learning experiences proceed.

1.1.2. *English Language Curricula in Türkiye*

The English language curricula implemented in Türkiye are centralized, specifically prepared, and mandated by the Ministry of National Education (MoNE). It suggests that state schools throughout Türkiye employ the same curricula. Türkiye offers two English language curricula. One is designated for primary and lower secondary education students in grades 2 to 8. Another is intended for an upper secondary education program with grades 9 to 12. Additionally, the MoNE has prepared and given free distribution of textbooks constructed in compliance with the curricula to the students, and English language teachers are responsible for implementing the textbooks in the classroom.

In 1997, the shift to eight years of compulsory education mandated English as the obligatory subject for fourth and fifth grades, focusing on student-centered learning within English language curricula (Kırkgöz, 2008). Having been a member of the Council of Europe in 2001, Türkiye started to apply CEFR and its principles to both English language curricula in 2002, 2011, and 2013 (Mirici, 2015). The English language curricula are developed by a backward design methodology. Curriculum designers begin by determining the targeted learning

outcomes (Richards, 2013) associated with the CEFR and subsequently work backward to establish suitable assessment tools, teaching materials, and instructional strategies. Then, the curricula undergo iterative evaluation, incorporating feedback from stakeholders such as academicians, educational administrators, teachers, students, and parents. In addition, pilot studies are conducted.

The present English language curricula were authorized in 2017, followed by pilot studies. On January 20, 2018, both were amended based on the results of the pilot studies and made available for use in the 2018-2019 school year (MoNE, 2018). The committee designated the current English language curricula, comprising various English language teachers from state schools, university professors, measurement and evaluation experts, and education professionals in the MoNE. Instead of emphasizing language usage, both curricula encourage students to use English as a communication method. The curricula comprise functional/notional syllabi, which are made up of 10 units containing language functions, objectives for listening, reading, speaking, and writing skills, as well as recommended activities and assignments for each grade. Reading skill is not included until 5th grade, and the teaching of writing skill starts in the 6th grade.

Table 1.
A sample unit from the curriculum of English as a foreign language (2-8 grades)

Unit / Theme	7 th Grade		
	Functions & Useful Language	Language Skills and Learning Outcomes	Suggested Contexts, Tasks and Assignments
10 Planets	<p>Making simple comparisons — Jupiter is larger than Saturn. — Uranus is cooler than Saturn.</p> <p>Talking about past events: When did scientists discover Pluto? In 2003, the Mars Exploration Mission began. They discovered evidence of water.</p> <p>Making simple inquiries Is there any water on the surface of Mars? Is there life in other planets? What do you know about our solar system? What do you know about planets? atmosphere, evidence, explore, galaxy, gravity, meteor, moon, observe, orbit, planet, proof rescue, satellite, shower, solar system, space shuttle, surface, universe</p>	<p>Listening E7.10.L1. Students will be able to identify the discussion topic about popular science in simple oral texts.</p> <p>Spoken Interaction E7.10.SI1. Students will be able to make simple comparisons.</p> <p>E7.10.SI2. Students will be able to talk about past events.</p> <p>Spoken Production E7.10.SP1. Students will be able to report on general truths in various ways.</p> <p>Reading E7.10.R1. Students will be able to identify specific information in various texts about facts and general truths.</p> <p>E7.10.R2. Students will be able to identify specific information about past events.</p> <p>Writing E7.10.W1. Students will be able to write short and basic descriptions of facts and general truths.</p>	<p>Contexts Blogs, Charts, Diaries/Journal Entries, E-mails, Illustrations, Lists, Magazines, Maps News, Reports, Notes and Messages, Podcasts, Posters</p> <p>Questionnaires, Songs, Stories, Tables, Videos, Websites Tasks/Activities</p> <p>Drama (Role Play, Simulation, Pantomime), Find Someone Who ..., Games, Guessing, Information/Opinion Gap, Information Transfer, Labeling, Matching, Questions and Answers, Reordering, Storytelling, True/False/No information Assignments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students complete and reflect on their visual dictionaries. • Students prepare a poster about our solar system and give information about the planets.

Note. Retrieved from *the Curriculum of English as a Foreign Language (2-8 Grades)*, by MoNE, 2018, p. 81.

Additionally, English language curricula in Türkiye provide a clear picture of the main philosophy, general objectives, testing and evaluation strategies, overall curriculum organization, and guidelines for applying them in detail. It can be gleaned that the curriculum development studies are executed point by point by the MoNE. In other words, curricula are established at the macro level and then used at the micro level by all the schools. Besides, the four components of the MoNE's curriculum development process, referred to as the Tyler-Taba model, are learning experiences, content, goals and objectives, and assessment (Demirel, 2005). Türkiye's English as a foreign language curriculum clearly identifies the anticipated outcomes of the program, including specific goals and objectives. Further, the curricula explain how values and norms are interconnected with these outcomes. The syllabus for each grade in the curricula comprises the content, linguistic functions, and grammatical structures to be taught. Units, functions, and learning outcomes are thoroughly stated, eliminating the need for teachers to develop syllabi for their classes. They encompass instructional methodologies and activities designed to facilitate learning while considering student-related factors such as motivation and learning strategies. They also receive information from the curricula regarding various assessment tools, including tests and portfolios, and utilizing them effectively.

Unlike English language teachers in other member nations of the Council of Europe, teachers in Türkiye are not obligated to design curricula or syllabi at the school or district level. They, however, are required to put these centralized curricula into practice as they intended, which may result in some practical issues. For instance, there can be a disparity between standardized content delivery and local needs regarding varied student demographics (Öztürk-Akar, 2022). Teachers' capacity to adapt their teaching methods depending on their students' level and needs can be limited by centralized curricula (Ayaz et al., 2019). To eliminate these practical issues, they must fully understand the curriculum (as its intended form) and incorporate it into their classes by assuring adherence for their students. They must possess proficiency in language skills, functions, and learning outcomes, as well as classroom activities, assessment, and theoretical knowledge to interpret the curricula effectively. Regarding the knowledge they must have, the current study aimed to address the research questions:

1. What is the curriculum literacy level of EFL teachers in Türkiye?
2. Are there any significant differences based on specific variables (i.e., years of experience, graduation programs, and language proficiency levels)?

2. Method

2.1. Research Design

This study, which sought to gauge English language teachers' curriculum literacy level, adopted a quantitative research design. By examining a population sample, a survey design offers a quantitative or numerical picture of that population's patterns, beliefs, and attitudes, enabling researchers to make generalizations or assumptions about the population based on sample results (Creswell, 2012). A survey design was also drawn on to depict, compare, contrast, categorize, evaluate, and interpret the entities (Cohen et al., 2017). A descriptive survey design was employed to answer research questions because it allows researchers to offer a realistic picture of current conditions using structured data collection tools to meticulously obtain information about participants without influencing the independent variables (Fowler, 2013).

2.2. Context

The study focused on teachers of English as a foreign language working in state primary, lower, and upper secondary schools in Türkiye. Holding a university-level degree in English language

teaching (ELT) is mandatory for teachers seeking employment as teachers of English in state schools. In addition, those who have completed degrees in linguistics, English language and literature, American culture and literature, translation, and interpreting studies can be eligible for employment upon completing a pedagogic teaching certificate program offered by specific faculties nationwide. These graduates from non-ELT programs are expected to properly execute the certificate program's compulsory courses, such as Introduction to Education, Teaching Principles and Methods, Testing and Evaluation, Instructional Technologies, Classroom Management, guidance, Special Teaching Methods, Educational Psychology, and Practicum. To be hired at state schools, English language teachers must pass the Public Personnel Selection Exam (KPSS), which is open to both ELT program graduates and those with pedagogic teaching certificates. This nationwide exam involves general skill questions covering Turkish language, mathematics, and geometry; world knowledge questions including geography, history, citizenship, and up-to-date information; educational sciences questions; and content knowledge questions to test teachers' field-specific competence. Having obtained above-average scores in the exam and face-to-face interview, they can commence employment in Turkish state elementary schools, lower secondary schools, or upper secondary schools based on their final scores. During their initial year, English language teachers start teaching actively and go through in-service training. At the end of the year, they must pass an exam hinged on their in-service training to complete their candidate teacher period. Apart from the stages English language teachers undergo to be attained at state schools, they are responsible for implementing English language curricula developed by the MoNE with the help of the coursebooks written in line with the curricula.

2.3. Participants

Participants in this study were English language teachers employed at state primary, upper, and secondary schools in Türkiye. There is not a single best sampling approach, according to Palys (2008), because it relies on the type and the context of the study. Simple random sampling was used to determine the participants for this study to minimize the influence of any external or subjective elements (Dörnyei, 2007). Simple random sampling ensures that all individuals within the study's universe have an equal opportunity to participate, thereby minimizing the researcher's influence on the sampling process. Regarding the number of participants, 804 English language teachers from every Türkiye region participated in this study.

Table 2.

Distribution of the participants

		N	Percentage
Programs	ELT	610	75.9
	Non-ELT	194	24.1
Years of experience	1-5 years	311	38.7
	6-10 years	198	24.6
	11-15 years	161	20.0
	16-20 years	95	11.8
	21-25 years	24	3.0
	26-30 years	15	1.9
English language proficiency scores	Not having a valid score.	294	36.6
	My score is between 0-49.	1	.1
	My score is between 50-59.	5	.6
	My score is between 60-69.	13	1.6
	My score is between 70-79.	85	10.6
	My score is between 80-89.	173	21.5
	My score is between 90-100.	233	29.0

As Table 2 shows, most of the participants were graduates of the ELT program. The majority of the teachers had ten years of experience or fewer. Almost a third of the teachers lacked a valid English proficiency result.

2.4. Data Collection Tool

The study collected data by employing an inventory to determine the degree of curriculum literacy among English language teachers. Using multiple-choice questions, the researchers of this study developed the Curriculum Literacy Inventory for Language Teachers (CLILT). Divided into two parts, CLILT has several demographic questions specifically addressing years of experience, graduation programs, and the language proficiency level of respondents in the first section. The second section of CLILT comprises twenty-five questions based on the five facets associated with the language curricula in Türkiye: learning outcomes and functions, language skills, activities, assessment, and theoretical knowledge to comprehend the curriculum. The initial step in determining the content of CLILT was to comprehensively analyze the literature on language curriculum and English language curricula in Türkiye. The following step involved conducting a focus group interview with five teachers of English as a foreign language who were involved in designing the English language curriculum by the MoNE. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with the three professors who participated in the English language curriculum development procedure arranged by the MoNE. In brief, both literature review and interviews played a role in forming the inventory content. The items were then written using the content framework. Three academicians with expertise in language curriculum development reviewed and approved the items, and then the first edition of CLILT was prepared for piloting. Following the pilot phase, several methods were utilized to test the validity and reliability of the inventory. These entailed analyzing each item's difficulty (P) and discrimination (D) and examining the factor loadings for each item.

The researchers utilized exploratory factor analysis to establish construct validity for the CLILT. A tetrachoric correlation coefficient (factor analysis) describing the linear relationship between two continuous variables, each of which was assessed on a dichotomous scale (Bonett & Price, 2005), was carried out because of the binary data (Lord & Novick, 1968) in the study. Moreover, it was necessary to assess the suitability of the participant data collected for factor analysis employing Bartlett's Test of Sphericity and the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Measure of Sampling Adequacy before beginning factor analysis of the questions (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013). Since the data from the pilot study had a KMO value of .712 and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity result of 0, factor analysis could be performed on it. The factor loadings for CLILT items were higher than the minimum value of .40, ensuring the construct validity (Thorkildsen, 2005) of CLILT.

Additionally, the internal consistency of CLILT was scrutinized via the Kuder-Richardson (KR) formula. Compared to Cronbach, which is utilized when responses are recorded for a scale, KR-20 is a better fit for CLILT because it comprises multiple-choice questions with a single correct answer. (Ding & Beichner, 2009). To ensure reliability, the item difficulty and item discrimination values of CLILT were also calculated in addition to the KR-20. Internal consistency is adequately addressed by the KR20 value of .849 for CLILT. With a mean discrimination value significantly greater than .30 and a mean difficulty value close to .50, the inventory has acceptable item difficulty (0.641) and item discrimination (0.511) values. In other words, CLILT is discriminatory in its assessment of language teachers' curriculum literacy levels, and it is neither too challenging nor too easy as a test.

The researchers and the subject matter experts decided on the criteria. They cut scores for CLILT based on its content and the results of the item analysis to interpret the data and to identify the level of curriculum literacy by determining whether participants' comprehension meets the pre-established requirements with criterion-referenced standards (Cizek, 2012; Norcini, 2003). Furthermore, the teachers were classified into three categories of curriculum-literate teachers: low, moderate, and high. This classification was determined by analyzing the P and D values of each question and considering the number of correct responses in both high and low groups. This classification was based on two cut scores, 60 and 80 out of 100, which were established as standards. Using a four-point rating system, the CLILT standard scale measures English language teachers' curriculum literacy. Teachers who answered at least 20 questions accurately were classified as highly curriculum-literate. Those who answered between 19 and 15 questions accurately were considered moderately curriculum-literate. In comparison, teachers who answered less than 15 questions accurately were categorized as having a low level of curriculum literacy (see Table 3).

Table 3.

Standards and Cut Scores of CLILT

<i>(0-59) A low level of curriculum literate English language teacher can</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • define language forms and their functions in a simple way. • recite learning outcomes in a plain way. • notice simple types of assessment and assessment tools. • recognize limited syllabus activities, steps of lesson planning and approaches of foreign language teaching. realize the small number of activities for learners' language skills.
<i>(60-79) A moderate level of curriculum literate English language teacher can</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • identify the relationship between language forms and their functions in a modest way. • interpret learning outcomes fairly. • realize the differences between language forms, their functions and learning outcomes in a simple way. • notice adequate types of assessment and assessment tools regarding their aims. • define a reasonable number of syllabus activities, steps of lesson planning and approaches of foreign language teaching as well as the relationship among them in an acceptable way identify the moderate number of activities for learners' language skills and their aims.
<i>(80-100) A high level of curriculum literate English language teacher can</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • analyze the relationship between language forms and their functions in an advanced way. • interpret learning outcomes effectively. • judge the differences between language forms, their functions and learning outcomes in detail. • determine the learning outcomes by associating language usage and their functions in language conclusively. • integrate approaches and methodologies of teaching foreign language into facilitating sophisticated syllabus activities and steps of lesson planning precisely. • identify a large number of activities for learners' language skills regarding their aims. apprehend numerous types of assessment and assessment tools regarding their aims to evaluate learners' progress in language learning appropriately.

2.5. Data Collection and Analysis

Data was gathered utilizing the MoNE's consent form and the informed consent form for participants. The participants were provided with a consent form that clearly outlined the objectives and extent of the study. With the consent form from the MoNE to collect data, the researchers successfully contacted volunteer English language teachers in state schools throughout all regions of Türkiye and gathered data online.

The normality of the data distribution was ensured by the sample size of the present study (Field, 2009; Pallant, 2007), which was examined using descriptive statistics and parametric

statistical tests to address each research question. Descriptive statistics were utilized to answer the first research question. Next, parametric tests were employed for the second question addressing the variables such as graduation program, years of experience and language proficiency level without applying a normality test thanks to the size of this study, which did not affect the validity of the results no matter whether the data are normally distributed or not (Altman, 1991; Elliott & Woodward, 2007; Ghasemi & Zahediasl, 2012; Hair et al., 2014; Pallant, 2007). Consequently, the graduation program variable was analyzed using the independent sample t-test, as it was divided into two categories: the ELT program and the non-ELT program. When a variable, such as years of experience or language proficiency level, had more than two independent groups, a one-way ANOVA was used to compare the means of test results obtained from each group.

3. Findings

The study used a hundred-point CLILT as a criterion-referenced test to gather data, revealing some information about English language teachers' curriculum literacy levels and how factors like years of experience, graduation program, and language proficiency affected those levels. The 25 multiple-choice questions in CLILT are hinged on the knowledge of the English language curriculum. This inventory has a total of 100 points since each correct response is worth four points. By averaging their CLILT results, 804 English language teachers' curriculum literacy level was found. The mean of the teachers' overall CLILT scores is depicted in Table 4.

Table 4.

Descriptive statistics of teachers' overall scores

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Score	804	16.0	100.0	63.80	21.1519
Valid N	804				

The table shows that the teachers' scores ranged from 16, the least, to 100, the greatest. When considering the pre-established CLILT standards, they had a moderate degree of curriculum literacy, as indicated by the mean of the overall scores, which was 63.80 out of 100. However, given that they were so close to the 60-point cut-off score, it is possible that English language teachers did not fully satisfy all the requirements outlined in the CLILT table for moderately curriculum-literate teachers. In addition, the percentage of the teachers who fell into the low, moderately, and highly curriculum-literate categories is presented in Table 5.

Table 5.

Descriptive statistics with CLILT cut scores

Cut Score	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
0-59	260	32.3	32.3	32.3
60-79	303	37.7	37.7	70.0
80-100	241	30.0	30.0	100.0
Total	804	100.0	100.0	

Around one-third of the teachers could poorly understand and interpret language curriculum. Moreover, about 38 of 100 teachers had a medium degree of proficiency in curriculum literacy. The 241 teachers with scores in the 80 to 100 range also demonstrated high curriculum literacy. This group, however, made up the smallest percentage. Only 30 of 100 teachers possessed high degree of curriculum literacy, while 70 did not.

Next, an independent sample t-test was operated to ascertain whether there was a statistically significant difference in total scores between the graduates of ELT and non-ELT programs.

Table 6.
Independent sample t-test of CLILT scores and graduate programs

	Program	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	t	SD	p
Score	ELT	610	65.692	21.1603	4.549	1.7225	.000
	Non-ELT	194	57.856	20.0440			

As demonstrated, the mean total scores exhibited a statistical difference ($p < .05$) concerning the program type they graduated from. Cohen's d value was 0.38, meaning these two groups clearly differ but not very strongly since 0.38 falls between 0.2 (small effect) and 0.5 (moderate effect). Regarding the scores obtained from the CLILT, ELT graduates answered 16 questions correctly on average, and non-ELT graduates had 14 correct answers on average. Concerning the cut scores, the teachers from ELT had a moderate level of literacy in the curriculum, whereas those without an ELT diploma exhibited a low level.

The results were also examined based on the teachers' years of experience, and this variable was divided into six categories (see Table 7).

Table 7.
One-way ANOVA of CLILT scores and years of experience

Factor	Experience	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	f	p
Score	1-5 years	311	64.129	22.3378	5.215	.000
	6-10 years	198	67.818	18.9524		
	11-15 years	161	64.050	20.1989		
	16-20 years	95	58.189	20.5852		
	21- 25 years	24	57.333	20.5208		
	26-30 years	15	47.200	23.3825		

For the average total scores, the ones with 6 to 10 years in school possessed the most significant mean; in contrast, the ones with 26 to 30 years of experience had the lowest mean. Remarkably, no group was found to exhibit a high level of proficiency in curriculum literacy. It was also revealed that the teachers in the first 15 years had a moderate level of program literacy, which then declined in the following years.

Table 8 indicated a significant difference in mean scores between English language teachers with 1-5 years of experience and those with 26-30 years of experience ($p < .05$). Teachers with five or fewer years of experience achieved scores approximately seventeen points higher than those with twenty-six or more years of experience. Secondly, the ones with 6-10 years of experience exhibited significant differences compared to those with 16-20 and 26-30 years of experience. The average score of respondents with 6-10 years of experience exceeded that of those with 16-20 years of teaching experience by 9.62 points and surpassed the scores of the ones with 26-30 years of experience by 20.61 points. A notable difference was found between English language teachers with 11-15 years of experience and those with 26-30 years of experience. Teachers with 11-15 years of experience scored 16.84 points, approximately four questions higher than those with 26-30 years of experience. Teachers with 16-20 years of experience differed statistically from those with 6-10 years of experience. Those with 16-20 years of experience scored 9.62 points lower than those with 6-10 years of experience. The data showed no significant difference between the group with 21-15 years of experience

and the other groups. Teachers with 25-30 years of experience exhibited significant differences compared to those with 1-5, 6-10, and 11-15 years of experience.

Table 8.

Tukey's post-hoc test for CLILT scores and years of experience

(I)Year of experience	(J)Year of experience	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
1-5 years	6-10 years	-3.6896	1.8983	.376
	11-15 years	.0789	2.0272	1.000
	16-20 years	5.9391	2.4476	.148
	21- 25 years	6.7953	4.4234	.641
	26-30 years	16.9286*	5.5196	.027
6-10 years	1-5 years	3.6896	1.8983	.376
	11-15 years	3.7685	2.2158	.532
	16-20 years	9.6287*	2.6059	.003
	21- 25 years	10.4848	4.5130	.186
	26-30 years	20.6182*	5.5916	.003
11-15 years	1-5 years	-.0789	2.0272	1.000
	6-10 years	-3.7685	2.2158	.532
	16-20 years	5.8602	2.7013	.253
	21- 25 years	6.7164	4.5687	.684
	26-30 years	16.8497*	5.6367	.034
16-20 years	1-5 years	-5.9391	2.4476	.148
	6-10 years	-9.6287*	2.6059	.003
	11-15 years	-5.8602	2.7013	.253
	21- 25 years	.8561	4.7701	1.000
	26-30 years	10.9895	5.8011	.406
21-25 years	1-5 years	-6.7953	4.4234	.641
	6-10 years	-10.4848	4.5130	.186
	11-15 years	-6.7164	4.5687	.684
	16-20 years	-.8561	4.7701	1.000
	26-30 years	10.1333	6.8723	.681
26-30 years	1-5 years	-16.9286*	5.5196	.027
	6-10 years	-20.6182*	5.5916	.003
	11-15 years	-16.8497*	5.6367	.034
	16-20 years	-10.9895	5.8011	.406
	21- 25 years	-10.1333	6.8723	.681

*The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Finally, the teachers' language proficiency variable was divided into five categories, and one category was designated for the teachers without a valid language proficiency exam result.

Table 9.

One-way ANOVA of CLILT scores and language proficiency

Factor	Language Proficiency	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	f	p
Score	Not have	294	59.755	20.0162	9.592	.000
	90-100	233	71.279	20.8152		
	80-89	173	62.312	20.7940		
	70-79	85	62.635	21.9745		
	60-69	13	53.538	21.6972		
	0-59	6	53.333	9.0037		

As seen, there is a considerable disparity between the overall results of the CLILT and the range of scores on the language proficiency exam. Noticeably, more than a third of the teachers asserted that they lacked a valid language exam result. The teachers who scored 70

or higher on their language proficiency examination were moderately curriculum-literate, unlike those who scored 69 or lower or without an official language proficiency score.

Table 10.
Tukey's post-hoc test for CLILT scores and language proficiency

(I) Scores	(J) Scores	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Not have	90-100	-11.5239*	1.8075	.000
	80-89	-2.5570	1.9747	.788
	70-79	-2.8802	2.5379	.867
	60-69	6.2166	5.8406	.895
	0-59	6.4218	8.4985	.975
90-100	Not have	11.5239*	1.8075	.000
	80-89	8.9668*	2.0682	.000
	70-79	8.6437*	2.6113	.012
	60-69	17.7405*	5.8729	.031
	0-59	17.9456	8.5207	.285
80-89	Not have	2.5570	1.9747	.788
	90-100	-8.9668*	2.0682	.000
	70-79	-.3232	2.7297	1.000
	60-69	8.7737	5.9264	.677
	0-59	8.9788	8.5578	.901
70-79	Not have	2.8802	2.5379	.867
	90-100	-8.6437*	2.6113	.012
	80-89	.3232	2.7297	1.000
	60-69	9.0968	6.1371	.676
	0-59	9.3020	8.7050	.894
60-69	Not have	-6.2166	5.8406	.895
	90-100	-17.7405*	5.8729	.031
	80-89	-8.7737	5.9264	.677
	70-79	-9.0968	6.1371	.676
	0-59	.2051	10.1710	1.000
0-59	Not have	-6.4218	8.4985	.975
	90-100	-17.9456	8.5207	.285
	80-89	-8.9788	8.5578	.901
	70-79	-9.3020	8.7050	.894
	60-69	-.2051	10.1710	1.000

*The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

In terms of the mean score on CLILT, the table showed that there was a difference between English language teachers who did not have a valid language proficiency score and those whose score was between 90 and 100. The teachers with a mean CLILT score between 90 and 100 were 11.52 points ahead of teachers who did not take a language test. Also, the ones who got a score of 90 to 100 on language tests were found to be statistically different from those who got scores of 80 to 89, 70 to 79, or 60 to 69 by 8.96, 8.64, and 9.64 points, respectively. The table also displayed no significant difference between the 0-59 score group and the others.

4. Discussion

In this study, the level of curriculum literacy of teachers of English as a foreign language was determined through the questions in CLILT. In his work, Shulman (1986) highlights the significance of teachers' comprehensive understanding of pedagogical content knowledge, subject matter content knowledge, and curricular knowledge. He explains that curricular knowledge entails the combination of pedagogical knowledge and subject matter knowledge.

Since CLILT includes questions related to the foreign language curricula designed in line with CEFR and theoretical field knowledge about applying them, English language teachers in Türkiye may not adequately possess this knowledge. So, they may experience some trouble implementing the curriculum properly. Since they are in charge of applying the curriculum in their classes, a lack of expertise in language curriculum may result in some misconceptions about what is intended (Taba, 1962; Schuchardt et al., 2017; Wiles & Bondi, 2007; Yasin et al., 2022). The effectiveness of a program ultimately lies in the hands of the teachers, regardless of how impeccable the curriculum may be. Competent teachers may frequently mitigate weaknesses in the curriculum, materials, or sources they deploy in their classroom instruction (Richards, 2001). Even though CEFR is utilized in designing English language curricula in Türkiye as other member countries do, the findings show that English language teachers in Türkiye may not implement the curricula properly, which can also be a result of teachers' lack of knowledge of CEFR underpinnings (Fişne et al., 2018).

In addition, Tsui (2003) puts forward that teachers who are less knowledgeable in their subject area are more likely to be overly prescriptive and stick rigidly to coursebooks; in contrast, teachers who are more knowledgeable in their subject area can critique coursebooks for their inappropriate parts and provide supplemental activities for practice and development. Considering the findings achieved in this study, English language teachers in Türkiye may strictly depend on the coursebooks that the MoNE has mandated. Regarding the coursebooks developed following the curricula in Türkiye, teachers may perceive coursebooks as curricula, which is why they can stick to them even though coursebooks are one of the curricula products. This can be another indication of their low proficiency in curriculum. In addition, it is postulated that high curriculum literacy enables teachers to liberate themselves from the shackles of coursebooks and conventions (Ben-Peretz, 1990); however, it may be deduced that “teachers frequently take and teach the textbook” (Fullan, 1982, p.118) in Türkiye because of their level of curriculum literacy. If teachers were more informed about the comprehensive nature of the curriculum, they would not strongly emphasize coursebooks. Understanding curriculum literacy can assist teachers in effectively addressing the challenges associated with the content covered in curriculum materials, the adaptation of the content to myriad student audiences, the trade-off between comprehensive coverage of topics and in-depth study of selected ones, the expertise necessary for using and generating educational materials, and autonomy in curriculum-related decision-making (Ben-Peretz, 1990). In Türkiye, where centralized English language curricula are carried out, it is pivotal that teachers aptly grasp curricular lines and the principles to eliminate possible challenges for implementation; nevertheless, the study results prove that they need to enhance their curriculum literacy.

Moreover, according to Berliner (1986), skilled teachers can blend the class objectives, time limits, and curriculum to lead the activity. However, this study discloses the fact that teachers of English as a foreign language in Türkiye do not exhibit high competency in curriculum, which suggests that there is room for improvement in areas such as approaches and methods to teach language skills, functions, and forms, learning outcomes, activities, assessment, and conceptual matters associated with lesson planning and language syllabus. Curriculum literacy of teachers of English as a foreign language can be elevated from a moderate to a high level by integrating areas of study about the teaching environment, curriculum, and subject matter into in-service training (Johnson, 2006). Nonetheless, in Türkiye, the focus of in-service training for language teachers has been primarily on foreign language teaching techniques and the use of technology in the classroom. These training opportunities include short-term courses and seminars (Özer, 2004). This leads to the conclusion that given the

absence of in-service training in language curriculum, the teachers in Türkiye demonstrate curriculum literacy levels between limited and moderate, a concern that was also highlighted by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) in 2007.

English language teachers' curriculum literacy is likely to vary when considering the length of time they are in the profession. The findings demonstrate that inexperienced teachers better understand the curriculum than their seasoned counterparts. One possible reason for this outcome may be that as teachers age, they may be more prone to forgetting what they learned during their undergraduate studies (Stevens, 1999) when they lack a chance to receive ongoing language instruction and curriculum training. Furthermore, national policies on foreign language learning, teaching practices, and technological advancements can lead to swift modifications in language curricula within the educational system. Specifically, the current language curricula developed in line with the CEFR tend to prioritize learner-centered approaches, but teacher-centered methods were more prevalent roughly two decades ago (Kırkgöz et al., 2016). Experienced teachers might have courses focusing on teacher-oriented approaches in their universities because learner-centered approaches have been a trend in Türkiye since the introduction of CEFR (Fişne et al., 2018). Therefore, the insufficient knowledge of changes in the profession and ineffective in-service teacher training held by the MoNE in implementing these modifications may be why experienced teachers have limited proficiency in curriculum literacy. This can also suggest their limited awareness of the CEFR theoretical underpinnings. This can be mitigated by in-service training so that they can stay current with the trends in the field.

Considering the graduation program, the present study shows a difference in curriculum literacy between non-ELT and ELT graduates. The level of curriculum literacy is found to be low among non-ELT graduates, while it is moderate among ELT graduates. This disparity may be attributed to the distinct composition of courses offered by the two programs. The ELT programs in Türkiye include field-specific courses such as teaching language skills, second language acquisition, teaching approaches and methodologies, teaching English to young learners, material adaptation and development, and English language testing and evaluation. Besides, in the courses about teaching English, there are microteaching sessions for student teachers. However, these courses are unavailable in non-ELT programs. In addition, non-ELT graduates enrolling in pedagogic teaching certificate programs can take pedagogical courses in educational sciences departments (Demiröz & Yeşilyurt, 2015). Unfortunately, they cannot have the opportunity to take field-specific courses. As highlighted in the literature, English language teachers knowledgeable in second language acquisition and teaching English methodologies can effectively deliver the curriculum content to the class (Pachler et al., 2007; Richards et al., 2013; Tsui, 2003). As a result, there exists a disparity in knowledge and skills between ELT and non-ELT graduates, and therefore, the graduates of non-ELT programs may face challenges in their understanding of the curriculum due to the lack of field-specific courses in their education. Conversely, English language teachers completing an ELT program cannot achieve a high level of curriculum literacy. Despite taking field-specific courses in an ELT program, they lack curricular understanding. The reason can be related to the fact that the ELT program falls short of finding a harmonious blend of theoretical and practical knowledge, resulting in inadequate preparation for classroom teaching (Demir, 2015). Studies indicate that numerous student teachers report dissatisfaction with the restricted opportunities for classroom observation and practical teaching experience during their education, resulting in inadequate preparation for the realities of the classroom (Cengiz, 2023; Öztürk & Aydın, 2019), where they can have opportunity to implement a curriculum. Similarly, Seferoğlu (2006) emphasizes the need for

ample opportunities for student teachers to experience actual teaching in Türkiye. Therefore, it can be concluded that although ELT graduates have some theoretical understanding, they may encounter specific practical challenges due to unfamiliarity with how the curriculum is implemented in classrooms during their university education. Moreover, the contents of both the pedagogic teaching certificate program and ELT program are determined by the Council of Higher Education (CoHE) in Türkiye at a macro level, and universities are expected to follow the regulations at a micro level, which may hinder the precautions that universities can take to adapt their contents for student teachers to gain more curriculum knowledge and have a chance to implement the curriculum.

Another potential determinant of curriculum literacy is the English language proficiency of teachers. English language teachers' classroom practices may be subpar if they have insufficient language skills (Richards & Farrell, 2005), as students have few chances to be exposed to English outside classrooms. Even if the centralized curricula display each unit in detail, teachers with low levels of English can teach the topic linguistically improperly, which can result in the curricula not being implemented as intended. Additionally, the classroom-level application of the curriculum by English language teachers may be impacted by their proficiency in the target language because the ones with limited proficiency in English may encounter challenges in comprehending teaching English approaches and notions in curricula. Conversely, those with a solid understanding of language can likely effectively comprehend and execute a language curriculum in the classroom.

5. Conclusion and Suggestions

Developing and piloting the data collection tool CLILT, the researchers sought to investigate the curriculum literacy level of teachers of English as a foreign language in Türkiye. However, this may be considered a limitation of the study. The researchers of this study designed a data collection instrument (CLILT) to assess the curriculum literacy of English language teachers, taking into account validity and reliability concerns. To ensure the validity of CLILT, both content validity and construct validity were established; however, criterion-related validity, which is demonstrated by comparing results from different instruments or the same instrument applied at different times, could not be attained. A potential explanation for this is the absence of a data collection instrument similar to CLILT, which hinders the opportunity for result comparison. Additionally, due to time constraints in conducting this study, CLILT could not be implemented twice with an extended interval. In addition, this study assessed internal consistency by measuring the KR20 value of CLILT and analyzing item difficulty and discrimination. However, it lacks reliability in terms of stability and equivalence. Moreover, the sample size ensured the normality of the data distribution in this study, so the researchers did not conduct tests to assess the homogeneity of variance for the gaps among some groups.

The study yielded some significant results highlighting that their curriculum literacy was at a moderate level, and graduation program, years of experience, and language proficiency affected the degree of this literacy. To assist teachers in becoming more curriculum-literate, the MoNE or universities may provide in-service training in curriculum design. The MoNE can also organize teacher training sessions to clarify the underpinnings of language curricula and CEFR implementation by inviting the academicians, MoNE officials, and teachers involved in developing language curricula. These training sessions should contain theoretical knowledge related to curriculum and interactive activities that allow teachers to debate and implement what they have learned. The MoNE should also take steps to avoid the danger of

teachers forgetting what they learned and keeping them up to date on educational advancements. By contacting experienced and novice teachers, the MoNE can plan in-service training in which both groups can exchange information. Furthermore, teaching certificate programs for non-ELT graduates may incorporate courses relevant to ELT, increasing their curriculum literacy. On the other hand, ELT programs can provide more opportunities for student teachers to practice their teaching in actual classrooms where they can implement the MoNE curricula.

The paramount aim of this study is to reveal English language teachers' curriculum literacy level; thus, it is not particularly concerned with the micro-level execution of the curriculum by these teachers. Additional studies on how they implement the curriculum in their classrooms may be worthy of developing a complete picture of curriculum literacy. Additionally, researchers aiming to investigate language curriculum literacy may reapply CLILT and compare their findings to enhance reliability as stability and criterion-related validity. Moreover, researchers aiming to create a data collection tool for assessing curriculum literacy among English language teachers or to modify CLILT can utilize the findings of this study to ensure reliability through equivalence.

Note

This paper is a product of the first author's master's thesis, supervised by the second author.

Ethical Issues

The authors confirm that ethical approval was obtained from Gazi University on 04/04/2019 and the Ministry of National Education on 17/05/2019 with the decision number 81576613-605.01-E9803634.

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

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